

Increasing spatial extent and frequency of flash drought in Europe with each degree of global warming

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Abstract. Flash droughts, characterised by sudden and severe development of dry soil moisture conditions, have detrimental impacts on agriculture and ecosystems. Since reliable projections of any kind of drought are crucial for drought risk mitigation, studying how these flash droughts might change as the Earth gets warmer becomes essential. Herein, we analyse changes in flash drought frequency, geographic extent, and regional variability across Europe under incremental global warming levels of 1°C, 1.5°C, 2°C and 3°C. Soil moisture simulations are obtained using the mesoscale Hydrologic Model (mHM), which has been forced with the bias-corrected meteorological data from ISIMIP3b (Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project, phase 3b). We use a percentile-based method to determine the rapid decline in soil moisture conditions during the growing season. Our results show that Northern and Central Europe are expected to see more frequent flash drought events at higher warming levels above 1.5°C. Central Europe is also becoming more vulnerable, with new areas experiencing frequent flash droughts as temperatures increase. In contrast, in the Mediterranean, the increase in frequency and area is less. Across Europe, we expect the mean frequency of flash droughts to increase from around 3 events each decade at 1°C to 5 events at 3°C. The median value of the spatial area covered in flash drought is expected to increase from around 30% at 1°C to close to 44% at 3°C. Each degree of increase in warming is expected to add around one more flash drought event each decade and more than 6% of the area across Europe under flash drought. Importantly, the threshold of 1.5°C marks a significant increase in the area affected by flash droughts, which highlights the importance of adhering to the Paris Agreement targets and adaptation measures to counter such flash drought conditions and safeguard the agricultural economy, food security, and ecosystems.

39 **1. Introduction**

40 Droughts are one of the most complex and least understood natural hazards (Pulwarty
41 and Sivakumar; 2014). Among them, “flash” droughts have emerged as distinct and
42 concerning climatic extremes. Flash droughts reduce soil moisture rapidly, with the
43 potential to cause damage to vegetation health without sufficient early warning, exposing
44 a different set of vulnerabilities in our agricultural system (Goswami and Gallant; 2025).
45 Flash droughts can be characterised by rapid onset and intensification in a span of a
46 few weeks, unlike conventional soil moisture droughts in which there could be a gradual
47 increase in soil moisture deficit for months if not years, posing a challenge to monitoring
48 and forecasting capabilities (e.g., Otkin et al.; 2018; Yuan et al.; 2019; Christian et al.;
49 2019). For example, the 2012 drought in the US heartland that started in the lower
50 Ohio Valley and eventually affected 65% of CONUS (contiguous United States) of which
51 20% of the area experienced extreme or exceptional drought conditions, causing a global
52 food security crisis along with \$30 billion agricultural losses (Boyer et al.; 2013). Even
53 more concerning was the rapid intensification, going from abnormally dry to the most
54 extreme drought category (D4) in just two months, as monitored by the U.S. Drought
55 Monitor (USDM; Svoboda et al.; 2002). This was not an isolated incident; several
56 previous studies have documented the occurrence of flash droughts in various parts of
57 the world, such as the 2010 flash drought in Russia (Christian et al.; 2020), Southern
58 China flash drought in 2013 (Yuan et al.; 2015), and Southern African flash drought
59 in 2015 (Yuan et al.; 2018). Moreover, studies show that there has been an increase
60 in such incidents in various parts of the world, like Brazil, where there has been an
61 increase in flash drought events between 1980 and 2015 (Christian et al.; 2021). Flash
62 droughts threaten agriculture and food security by significantly lowering gross primary
63 productivity (e.g., Ford and Labosier; 2017; Christian et al.; 2021; Jing et al.; 2025).

64 The atmospheric conditions antecedent to these flash drought events are
65 precipitation deficits and high temperatures, causing an increase in the evaporative
66 demand (Ford and Labosier; 2017; Pendergrass et al.; 2020; Shah et al.; 2023; Zeng
67 et al.; 2023). In addition to these conditions, compound meteorological extremes such as
68 concurrent heat waves and precipitation deficit play an important role in the occurrence
69 of flash droughts (Christian et al.; 2020; Wang et al.; 2023). Several recent studies
70 also analysed, the projected changes in the frequency of flash drought events according
71 to different emission scenarios (SSPs) to see how these flash droughts are expected
72 to develop and the trends indicate an increment (e.g., Christian et al.; 2021; Naumann
73 et al.; 2021; Sreeparvathy and Srinivas; 2022; Christian et al.; 2023, among others). Yuan
74 et al. (2023) in their study highlighted that the global shift from slow-onset droughts
75 to flash droughts is driven by climate change caused by human activities, emphasising
76 the evolving nature of flash droughts in a warming climate. A study by Yuan et al.
77 (2019) showed that greenhouse gas emissions (GHGs) are responsible for more than
78 77% of the observed increase in flash drought incidents across China, indicating the
79 role of anthropogenic causes. Thus, it can be said that anthropogenic warming plays a

80 role in altering these flash drought events into the future. Europe encompasses alpine,
81 maritime, Mediterranean, and continental climates, such climatic and environmental
82 heterogeneity demands more focused regional study to see the development of flash
83 drought in future, based on which more nuanced mitigation and adaptation strategies
84 can be developed. A study by Christian et al. (2024) analysed existing research on flash
85 droughts, dividing them by region, countries and global scale, highlighting the lack of
86 regional studies for Europe (four in total by then) compared to other regions like the
87 US and China (48 each). Thus, it can be said that despite these recent advancements,
88 there is a lack of assessment of how flash droughts may evolve, especially in terms of
89 different global warming scenarios, specifically in the European context.

90 The aim of this study is to address the lack of regional studies specific to Europe,
91 focusing on how flash droughts may change with different levels of global warming
92 for better policy implementation approaches. A warming level approach takes into
93 account the differences among various GCMs (General Circulation Models) in each SSP
94 (Socioeconomic Pathways) scenario in terms of meteorological conditions over the 31-
95 year climatological period. A warming level-based ensemble of various projected models
96 represents the development of flash droughts under similar environmental conditions,
97 specifically temperature. This helps reduce the uncertainties related to differences
98 in climate sensitivity between models, which enables a clearer detection of regional
99 patterns (Vautard et al.; 2014). The 1°C serves as a baseline for the study, and we
100 analyse the warming levels up to 3°C. We analyse the frequency and spatial extent along
101 with regional variability of flash droughts across Europe using the ISIMIP3b dataset.
102 Our study uses pentad-based soil moisture obtained through the spatially distributed
103 mesoscale Hydrologic Model (mHM). We examine rapid soil moisture declines to
104 identify flash droughts. Additionally, the study investigates the underlying driving
105 meteorological factors, like temperature and precipitation anomalies, pertaining to the
106 soil moisture conditions that are causing these flash droughts. At the end, the sensitivity
107 of the frequency and the area are analysed with respect to each degree of warming. Our
108 goal is to enhance our understanding of flash drought in a warming world, which in
109 turn will help to mitigate the impacts and adapt accordingly. It will be helpful for
110 policymakers targeting a particular level of warming-based strategies.

111 **2. Data and Methods**

112 *2.1. Meteorological input data representing global warming levels*

113 Meteorological data used to identify flash drought events are primarily based on the
114 Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project (ISIMIP3b; Warszawski et al.;
115 2014; Lange and Büchner; 2021), which is based on simulations from the Coupled
116 Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6; O'Neill et al.; 2016). These data
117 cover both historical conditions (1950–2014) and future projections (2015–2100) under
118 three Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs): SSP1-2.6, SSP3-7.0, and SSP5-8.5,

119 representing different levels of greenhouse gas emissions and socioeconomic development
120 (O'Neill et al.; 2014). We use output from five General Circulation Models (GCMs):
121 GFDL-ESM4, IPSL-CM6A-LR, MPI-ESM1-2-HR, MRI-ESM2-0, UKESM1-0-LL under
122 each SSP scenario. These GCMs are used because of their structural uniqueness and
123 collective representation of the broader CMIP6 ensemble (Rosa and Sangiorgio; 2025).
124 These data are available at daily temporal resolution and at the $0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$ spatial
125 resolution. Since this study focuses on different levels of global warming, we do not
126 directly use the SSP time series. A period of ± 15 years around the year when that
127 particular warming is reached in the different SSP-GCM combinations is used for the
128 analysis (Lange and Büchner; 2021; ISIMIP; 2021) (see Table S1 for warming level years).
129 This period is decided on the basis of ISIMIP3b, which utilises a 31-year moving average
130 (Lange and Büchner; 2021), which also leads to the removal of short-term fluctuations
131 in the data (Pierce et al.; 2015).

132 *2.2. Methodology*

133 *2.2.1. Soil Moisture simulations and conversion to Soil Moisture Index (SMI)*

134 Daily precipitation and 2 m air temperature (average, minimum and maximum)
135 data from the ISIMIP3b, bi-linearly downscaled to $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$, are used to force the
136 mesoscale Hydrologic Model (mHM; Samaniego et al.; 2010; Kumar et al.; 2013) to
137 simulate root-zone soil moisture. We employ the European mHM setup, which has
138 been thoroughly evaluated in previous studies against multiple hydrological variables,
139 including river discharge, evapotranspiration, soil moisture and terrestrial water storage
140 anomaly (e.g., Rakovec et al.; 2016; Kumar et al.; 2020; Pohl et al.; 2023; Droppers
141 et al.; 2024; Bevacqua et al.; 2024). Our analysis focuses on the top 30 cm soil layer,
142 corresponding to the near-surface root zone, where over 50% of global root biomass is
143 typically found (Schenk and Jackson; 2002). This depth is important for vegetation,
144 which is vulnerable to soil moisture depletion during flash droughts in the vegetation
145 period (Moreno et al.; 2005; Fan et al.; 2016; Shah et al.; 2022), and can affect vegetation
146 health (Ford and Labosier; 2017; Otkin et al.; 2018; Mishra et al.; 2021; Sungmin and
147 Park; 2023).

148 To reduce the influence of short-term variability, daily soil moisture simulations are
149 aggregated into 5-day pentads. This way, we reduce the noise due to inter-day variability
150 caused by various transient atmospheric phenomena and short-term fluctuations in
151 temperature and precipitation, and the reliability of the study increases (Koster et al.;
152 2019, 2021). It also increases the reliability of yearly variation comparison for the
153 corresponding pentads. Therefore, in line with studies like Shah et al. (2022); Zeng
154 et al. (2023); Sungmin and Park (2023, 2024) among others, this study also follows the
155 pentad system instead of studying daily soil moisture data.

156 Given the strong regional differences in climate, soil, and vegetation across Europe,
157 we convert pentad soil moisture values into standardised Soil Moisture Index (SMI) for
158 each grid using the non-parametric Gringorten plotting position method (Gringorten;

159 1963) to allow meaningful comparisons across space and time (Shah et al.; 2022).
160 First, we obtain the Gringorten-based distribution function curve over each grid for the
161 respective pentad in the growing season for the historical period of 1950–2014. Then,
162 we apply these historical distributions to the corresponding pentads in the future period
163 (2015–2100) to calculate SMI values for each of the SSP-GCM separately.

164 *2.2.2. Flash drought identification*

165 We use the SMI to obtain flash drought events during the growing season (i.e. 19–
166 55 pentads out of 73 in each year), following the study by Shah et al. (2022). For this,
167 the respective pentads of each year are utilised for each grid to get the SMI based on soil
168 moisture conditions in the future and then later flash drought events. Supplementary
169 Figure S1 shows the schematic of the flash drought definition. The flash drought is
170 initiated when SMI falls from a mark above the 40th percentile to below the 20th
171 percentile in less than three continuous pentads. Also, there should be a consistent
172 decline in the SMI at the mean intensification rate of 0.1 per pentad, therefore fulfilling
173 the condition of rapid decline (Otkin et al.; 2018). The flash drought event is marked
174 as terminated when the SMI rises to above the 20th percentile and stays there for
175 at least two continuous pentads, eliminating a single abnormal event of rise in SMI.
176 Only the drought events lasting between 6 to 18 pentads were considered, ensuring the
177 elimination of short-term abnormality and differentiation from long-term drought events
178 (conventional droughts) (e.g. Yuan et al.; 2019; Mahto and Mishra; 2020; Mishra et al.;
179 2021; Pendergrass et al.; 2020).

180 We obtain the flash droughts events for the period 1950–2100 across Europe, which
181 are further decomposed into three SREX regions defined by IPCC (Figure 1(a)), viz.,
182 Northern (NEU) and Central Europe (CEU) and the Mediterranean (MED)) (Murray
183 and Ebi; 2012). These flash drought events are then later used to synthesize the results
184 at various warming levels according to the year in which that warming is achieved (see
185 Table S1 for warming-level years).

186 *2.2.3. Experimental Design for analysis under various warming levels*

187 Flash drought conditions, identified under each SSP-GCM combination, are
188 analysed to determine their frequency and spatial extent across various warming levels.
189 For each warming level, the frequency of flash drought is calculated per grid cell using
190 an ensemble of up to 15 SSP-GCM combinations. This per-grid frequency is then
191 normalised by dividing by the number of combinations available for that warming
192 level, as some warming levels might not be achieved in certain SSP-GCM combinations
193 (see Table S1, which contains the year, for each SSP-GCM combination, in which a
194 warming level is reached). After obtaining the number of flash drought events for the
195 entire duration of 31-years for each warming level, we can get an annual frequency.
196 Besides frequency, we also estimate the spatial extent of the area under flash drought
197 at a particular warming level. For each SSP-GCM in the event of a flash drought
198 occurrence, the total area covered in that year is obtained during the 31-year period

199 duration. These areas obtained through each SSP-GCM combination are then used to
200 get a density distribution ridge plot for each warming level for Europe as well as the
201 three European regions (NEU, CEU and MED). Since flash droughts at a soil depth of
202 30 cm are more threatening for our agricultural crops, it becomes important to study
203 that as well. Therefore, we also conducted the analysis to examine projected changes
204 in flash drought characteristics for various land cover types (cropland, pastureland and
205 forest). The LUH2 (Land Use Harmonization², Hurtt et al.; 2020) dataset is utilized for
206 this purpose.

207 Furthermore, temperature and precipitation anomalies are calculated from the
208 ISIMIP3b dataset to understand how the flash droughts vary with changing temperature
209 and precipitation anomalies under different warming levels, and where they are
210 concentrated. For this, a 31-year ensemble mean baseline of 1°C is calculated for
211 the respective pentads for each grid, which are utilised to calculate anomalies of the
212 corresponding pentads again for each grid separately. The 1°C is selected as a baseline
213 as that represents the most recent past global temperature (2017 to be precise) according
214 to IPCC (Masson-Delmotte et al.; 2018; IPCC; 2018). As mentioned in the IPCC (2018)
215 report, human-induced warming reached approximately 1.0°C (likely between 0.8°C and
216 1.2°C) above pre-industrial levels by 2017. The 3°C warming level is chosen as that
217 represents the future projections if the emission path continues without sustainable
218 policies and uninhibited emissions (Rosa and Sangiorgio; 2025). The 1.5°C and 2°C are
219 used as they form the central part of the Paris Agreement (Paris Agreement; 2015).
220 Based on the anomalies obtained, a regional temperature and precipitation anomaly
221 is calculated for a particular pentad across all SSP-GCM combinations. Anomalies
222 of the drivers are aggregated and binned, and based on this, bi-variate heat maps are
223 created showcasing these binned temperature-precipitation anomalies with flash drought
224 events (pixels that are under flash drought condition during that pentad). As these
225 flash drought pixels are aggregated from all the SSP-GCM combinations, they are later
226 normalised according to the number of combinations available for a particular warming
227 level. Once we get a heat map of each region (viz., NEU, CEU and MED), they are
228 aggregated bin-wise to get the entire European heat map.

229 Finally, we carry out a sensitivity analysis to understand how the frequency and area
230 of these flash droughts vary as global warming increases. We make two separate profiles
231 using a linear fit for frequency and area. The line is fit into the scatter plot containing
232 a number of flash drought events on each pixel for the duration of a 31-year period of
233 that warming level for each SSP-GCM combination. These flash drought events are
234 normalised according to the number of combinations available for each warming level.
235 Also, the mean value of flash drought at each warming level of all these available SSP-
236 GCM combinations is also represented in the plot. For the area characteristic profile,
237 mean values of the area under flash drought are calculated and used for the linear fit.

238 3. Results and Discussion

239 3.1. Frequency of flash drought in Europe under different warming levels

240 Figure 1 shows the number of flash drought events in the 31-year period and their
241 changes under different global warming levels (1°C, 1.5°C, 2°C and 3°C), which are
242 derived from an ensemble of SSP scenarios of the CMIP6 models. FD Count in
243 Figure 1(a)-(d) represents the number of flash drought events in the window of the
244 warming level year in which the SSP-GCM combination reaches the analysed warming
245 level ± 15 years around the year (normalised on each grid for the number of combinations
246 available). Results illustrate an overall increase in the number of flash drought events,
247 with the results being more pronounced in the Northern and Central parts of Europe
248 and less so in the Mediterranean region, showing regional disparities. Northern and
249 Central Europe exhibited a higher number of flash drought events, particularly at higher
250 warming levels. We observe the red patches (in Figure 1) increasing from 1°C to 3°C,
251 with some going as high as above 30, implying an almost annual frequency under the
252 highest warming scenario. The Northern and Central European regions typically exhibit
253 higher baseline soil moisture due to more frequent precipitation. In such wet/transitional
254 climates, flash droughts can quickly form when high evaporative demand coincides with
255 short precipitation deficits; in contrast, however, the Mediterranean has a moisture-
256 limited climate, so even if evaporative demand is high, actual evapotranspiration that
257 occurs is less because the soil is already dry (Manning et al.; 2018).

258 To understand the relative percentage changes in flash drought numbers,
259 Figure 1(e)-(g) presents these changes corresponding to Figure 1(b)-(d), with respect
260 to the 1°C baseline. A large area of Europe going from green to brown implies the
261 spreading and development of new hotspots and also the frequent nature of such
262 events at higher warming as we move from 1.5°C to 3°C. Several areas, particularly
263 in Northern Europe, like Sweden and Finland, exhibit a 100% increase in flash drought
264 occurrence, suggesting a potential doubling of the number of events in those areas if
265 we continue our emission pathway and the warming reaches 3°C. The spatial map
266 of flash droughts indicates emerging hot spots of flash droughts in Central Europe,
267 which historically were less impacted by such droughts. The sudden outbursts of brown
268 spots at 2°C depict it as a critical threshold. Along some coastlines as well, we see
269 an increase in the events, indicating the possibility of some local maritime factors
270 being responsible, like warm sea surface temperatures and persistent high-pressure
271 systems, which can suppress convective precipitation, intensifying drought conditions in
272 coastal Mediterranean regions (Wang and Yuan; 2022). So, even though, lower synoptic
273 variability in the Mediterranean, unlike in the northern and central European regions,
274 limits the frequent atmospheric changes that can lead to conditions of flash drought
275 (Manning et al.; 2018), the local factors coupled with coastal dynamics such as salinity
276 intrusion and reduced freshwater inflows further amplify drought stress in deltaic and
277 estuarine zones, highlighting the complex interplay between land-ocean-atmosphere
278 systems in modulating Mediterranean flash drought vulnerability (Xu et al.; 2023).

279 Supplementary Figure S2 shows the number of flash drought events at six different
280 warming levels with an addition of 0.5°C and 2.5°C. Here, the abrupt change at 2°C is
281 even more evident despite the presence of some red spots at 1.5°C. However, at 2°C,
282 the patches of blue indicate that lower values are completely overshadowed, suggesting
283 a steeper increment from that point.

284 Figure 1 (h) shows a box plot of the average number of flash droughts that a grid
285 cell is expected to experience in the window of those 31 years at that warming level
286 in different European regions. It illustrates the number of events in the future under
287 an increased global warming environment. The number is projected to increase from
288 around three flash drought events every decade at 1°C warming level to more than
289 5 events at 3°C, indicating a 50% or more probability in any given year and almost
290 double the number of events compared to 1°C. Box-plot also suggests more events in
291 the Northern and Central parts of Europe compared to the Mediterranean. There is
292 an increase in every region, but the effects are more pronounced in the Northern and
293 Central parts. Mediterranean shows lower numbers in comparison; local hot spots,
294 however, do exist along the Mediterranean coastline. Even though the Mediterranean
295 region shows relatively stable conditions with fewer extremes, localised risks are there
296 in regions like Spain, Italy, and several Balkan regions. There is a broader increase
297 in high-frequency zones between 1.5°C and 2°C, indicating increased sensitivity and
298 the widespread expansion of flash droughts. The Mediterranean also shows a slower
299 escalation compared to the Northern and Central European regions.

300 *3.2. Spatial extent of flash droughts in Europe under different warming levels*

301 Figure 2 (a) shows distributions of total area that was affected in the case of a flash
302 drought event across Europe under different warming levels. Area under the ridges is
303 demarcated by a 40% flash drought area line. We observe a consistent rise in the spatial
304 extent of flash droughts as global warming intensifies from 1°C to 3°C. Notably, Figure 2
305 (a) shows that the area at 1°C warming is predominantly below 40% (around 13% area
306 under the curve is above 40%), which is in striking contrast to more than 71% area under
307 curve reaching above 40% at 3°C warming. The increment implicates a gradual increase
308 with almost linear amplification in flash drought extent. This increase is especially
309 noticeable in Northern and Central Europe, where flash droughts affect more than 60%
310 of the area in some cases, even at a 1.5°C warming level, see Figure 2(b), (c). By 3°C,
311 the area reaching 40% in a given year becomes more common compared to lower levels
312 of global warming.

313 Regional heterogeneity is evident across Northern and Central Europe especially
314 demonstrating pronounced susceptibility with flash drought areas close to 47% at 3°C
315 compared to 36% in the Mediterranean at the same warming level as shown in Figure 2
316 (b)-(e). Whiskers exceed 60% in both Northern and Central Europe. In contrast to
317 these two regions, the Mediterranean is relatively stable, which could be due to a
318 permanent shift in soil moisture conditions due to increased aridity (Silvestri et al.;

2025). Therefore, Northern and Central Europe require urgent and aggressive measures to cope with such droughts, while the Mediterranean require heightened resilience strategies. Such trends reaffirm the necessity of adherence to a global warming level of 1.5°C.

We have also studied area coverage in flash drought incidents across various land cover types as well (see Supplementary Figures S3, S4, S5). We observe a similar pattern across various land covers. In croplands, the area under the curve exceeding 40% is around 67% with median lying at around 44% of the cropland area across the entire Europe. In case of croplands, Central Europe is expected to be slightly more affected than Northern Europe, both of which have comparatively higher areas affected by flash drought events compared to the Mediterranean. In case of pastureland, the median for the entire European region lies at 43% with more than 61% of the area under the curve being higher than 40%. Northern and Central European pasturelands median area affected in case of a flash drought occurrence is above 50%, while it is close to 37% in case of the Mediterranean. In forests, even though it is not expected to be affected much in case of only top 30 cm of soil, the median area affected in a flash drought event is close to 50% for the entire European region.

3.3. Meteorological drivers of flash drought

Figure 3 shows heatmaps of flash drought events throughout Europe at various warming levels, along with their relative changes. These heatmaps depict the evolution of flash drought occurrences under different temperature and precipitation anomalies at each warming level. Panel (a) shows the number of grids on which flash drought event occurs at 1°C warming level at various temperature and precipitation anomalies. The 1°C warming level serves as the baseline. At 1°C, we can see the flash drought events are mostly concentrated in the moderate to higher precipitation deficit and small temperature anomalies (can be observed through the 90% contour line that encloses the bins in which 90% of the flash drought grids/pixels are located). Panels (b), (c), and (d) show the same characteristics but for 1.5°C, 2°C, and 3°C warming levels. As we move to the higher warming level compared to pre-industrial levels, we observed that the maximum occurrence of flash drought events (the concentration of clusters of higher flash drought count) shifts towards a hotter and drier climate, i.e., still moderate to higher precipitation deficits but higher temperature anomalies. This also hints at the role of precipitation, as even though there might be a shift of the number of grids towards higher temperature bins, the same amount of precipitation deficit is still required. That, however, does not mean that the role of elevated temperatures can be undermined. A study by Qing et al. (2022) suggested that a high percentage of flash drought-affected areas is not always accompanied by high temperatures. In our study we can see a few instances at lower temperatures, where in the case of extreme precipitation deficit, we can have flash drought, but the number is not significant. According to our results for the most part flash drought is accompanied with higher temperatures. Higher absolute

359 differences and relative change can be seen from 2°C onward. Even though there is
360 a slight decrease in the flash drought events in a lower deficit and cooler climate, the
361 difference is overshadowed by the significant increase in the hotter and drier conditions,
362 as we can see from the absolute differences between the number of grids going through
363 the flash drought event. The higher absolute difference at higher temperature and
364 precipitation anomalies emphasises a worsening effect on flash drought events with
365 increasing global warming due to climate change.

366 Panels (e), (f) and (g) show the relative changes indicate asymmetric change, i.e.,
367 a more substantial and much more pronounced increase than decrease, leading to an
368 overall much higher count of flash drought events at higher warming levels. The darker
369 shade with higher absolute differences indicates the exacerbation of flash drought events
370 caused by a warming climate. Similar patterns can be observed in the Supplementary
371 Figure S6, S7, S8 with the absolute differences being highest at higher warmings. In
372 all three European regions (NEU, CEU and MED), the small decrease in such events at
373 negative temperature anomalies is overshadowed by the higher absolute differences at
374 higher warming levels. For precipitation deficits in Northern Europe, the entire range
375 from lower precipitation deficits to higher can be seen, with a concentration of high flash
376 drought counts. It is centred towards the moderate precipitation deficits in the case of
377 Central Europe and higher precipitation deficits in the case of the Mediterranean.

378 An overall increase in the number suggests that flash droughts will be much more
379 common in Europe with future warming. As the study by Řehoř et al. (2024) also
380 suggested that the course of flash drought episodes was also connected to increased
381 temperatures and often connected to warm airflow. Results imply that mitigation efforts
382 are required to keep the warming under 2°C in accordance with the Paris Agreement
383 (Paris Agreement; 2015) to decrease the risk of a higher number of flash drought events
384 due to increased warming. The occurrence of such events at lower warming levels
385 also suggests the importance of adaptation strategies along with mitigation efforts to
386 safeguard our agricultural, economic, and food security concerns.

387 *3.4. Sensitivity of characteristics of flash droughts to warming*

388 Figure 4 synthesises the aforementioned results in terms of the sensitivity of the number
389 of events and the area affected to each degree of global warming. The results show
390 that for both characteristics, there is an increase towards higher levels of warming.
391 Panel (a) depicts the sensitivity to warming for the number of flash droughts. We
392 observe that Northern Europe has the highest slope, so it is most sensitive to warming
393 for flash drought events, followed by Central Europe and the Mediterranean. While
394 Central Europe has the highest intercept, indicating a greater initial number of events,
395 Northern Europe's higher sensitivity leads to catching up to the numbers of Central
396 Europe because of higher sensitivity to warming. In the entire Europe, we can observe
397 that for the period of those 31 years, with each degree increase in global warming
398 compared to pre-industrial levels, we observe around three more flash drought events.

399 This is approximately one more event during each decade for each degree of warming.

400 Similarly, Figure 4 (b) presents the sensitivity of the area of flash drought to
401 warming. Here, as well, Northern Europe exhibits the highest slope, showing higher
402 sensitivity, followed by Central Europe and the Mediterranean. The intercept is again
403 higher in the case of Central Europe, but only by a slight margin, but overall, the
404 percentage area under flash drought in the region is higher in the case of Northern
405 Europe due to greater sensitivity. Although the area of Central Europe is more than
406 that of Northern Europe, the overall area under flash drought is greater in the case of
407 Central Europe. We can see from the slope of the entire Europe that for each degree
408 increase in warming annually, more than 6% of the area will come under flash droughts.
409 In both cases, the Mediterranean has the lowest slope and intercept, but still, there is
410 an overall increase in the frequency and area in the Mediterranean as well.

411 In case of specific land cover types, croplands and pasturelands are expected to
412 have two more events, and forest is expected to have three more events. Croplands
413 and pasturelands are expected to be more affected in the case of Central Europe, while
414 forests are expected to be most affected in the case of Northern Europe, looking at the
415 slopes of the linear fit. Area under flash drought is expected to increase by 6% in the
416 case of croplands, 5% in the case of pasturelands and 7% in the case of forests with each
417 degree of warming. The area follows the same pattern as the number of events, with
418 the most affected area in the case of croplands and pasturelands in Central Europe, and
419 the most affected area under a flash drought event in forests being highest in Northern
420 Europe.

421 *3.5. Implications and Discussions*

422 Flash drought frequency historically has increased not just across Europe (Shah et al.;
423 2022) but across the globe (Christian et al.; 2021). There is a shift happening towards the
424 flash drought (Yuan et al.; 2019) because of the anthropogenic causes (GHG emissions).
425 Even though there have been many studies highlighting the unprecedented increase in
426 conventional droughts in recent years (Hari et al.; 2020; Büntgen et al.; 2021; Rakovec
427 et al.; 2022), more studies are required in the field of flash droughts. Several recent
428 studies like Sreeparvathy and Srinivas (2022) have indicated an increase in such events,
429 especially in higher emission scenarios like SSP585. In general, soil moisture droughts
430 are expected to rise due to anthropogenic causes (Samaniego et al.; 2018), so due to
431 increased evaporative demand exacerbated by increased temperature and precipitation
432 deficits, flash droughts are projected to be more frequent. Study by Gu et al. (2025)
433 suggested flash droughts accompanied by extreme heat exhibit higher severity and
434 longer recovery time than flash droughts without extreme heat which also raises alarms
435 regarding occurrence of such events at higher warming. Flash drought with other
436 compound extremes like a concurrent heatwave can impose an additional significant
437 threat to our agricultural crops and ecosystems, as highlighted in a regional study by
438 Wang et al. (2023) how concurrent heatwaves can cause temporally shorter but faster-

439 occurring flash droughts.

440 Our study reveals an increasing sensitivity of flash droughts in Europe to each
441 degree of rise in global warming. While previous projection studies exist, examining
442 these projections in the context of rising warming levels is crucial for policymakers to
443 develop warming-level-based strategies. Our findings align with global projections, such
444 as Yuan et al. (2023), which anticipate more flash drought occurrences across the globe,
445 especially over relatively more humid regions like Europe. This phenomenon can be
446 attributed to the fact that, as evapotranspiration over these regions is energy-limited,
447 enhanced radiation due to reduced cloud cover leads to an increase in evapotranspiration
448 and speeds up drought onset. Importantly, Yuan et al. (2023)'s global analysis also
449 indicates a more rapid development and higher frequency of flash droughts towards
450 Northern Europe, similar to the findings of our study.

451 Higher emission scenarios are of amplified threat (Sreeparvathy and Srinivas; 2022)
452 as these are the ones that will cause higher warming levels. Our study demonstrates
453 that these higher warming levels carry an increased risk, especially beyond the pivotal
454 1.5°C threshold. Some regional studies within Europe, e.g., Noguera et al. (2020), show
455 the higher occurrence in summer (the growing season in our study) and that 40% of all
456 droughts were characterised by rapid development. We also found that Spain, among
457 many other regions, emerges as a new hotspot for such flash drought events. A study
458 by Sungmin and Park (2023) shows the rapid vegetation stress caused by these events,
459 amplifying the need for adaptation and mitigation measures. Our study shows the
460 importance of Paris Paris Agreement (2015) to keep the global warming “well below
461 2°C above pre-industrial levels and pursuing efforts to limit the temperature increase to
462 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels” (Climate Action Tracker; 2021).

463 **4. Conclusions**

464 We have quantified the sensitivity of flash drought frequency and affected area across
465 Europe with each degree of global warming. This study projects how flash droughts will
466 evolve based on an ensemble of five General Circulation Models under three different
467 Shared Socioeconomic Pathways. Our analysis indicates that as the global temperature
468 rises, Europe will experience a significant increase in the number of flash drought events.
469 Furthermore, areas historically less susceptible to these events may not be safe, leading
470 to the development of new flash drought hotspots. It is expected that there will be
471 one additional flash drought event per decade for each degree of warming. The spatial
472 extent of area under flash drought is expected to increase by 6% with each degree rise in
473 global warming in Europe. Our study also reveals that precipitation anomalies towards
474 the deficit in conjunction with elevated temperatures are the drivers behind the increase
475 in flash drought events in the future.

476 This study also provides a framework that can be adopted for other regional-
477 level studies or global-scale assessments. Further study is needed to understand the
478 impacts associated with such flash droughts and to identify effective mitigation and

479 adaptation measures. Another aspect of future study could be to explore how large-
480 scale atmospheric phenomena affect the occurrence of such events as Chen et al.
481 (2019) found out that flash droughts over the United States are largely related to La
482 Niña episodes or as the study by Mahto and Mishra (2023) found out that positive phase
483 of El Niño Southern Oscillation influences flash drought co-occurrence in 10 out of 16
484 major cropland regions and remains a dominating factor of flash droughts co-occurrence
485 in the future. Another aspect could be to explore how vegetation and its type affect
486 flash drought, which will require a regional study as well, as the study by Sungmin and
487 Park (2024) shows heterogeneous responses to ecological impacts. These aspects are
488 currently out of the scope of this study but can be further extended comprehensively in
489 future studies. It can be concluded that with rise in warming flash drought are going to
490 rise in numbers and in area. With its detrimental effect on crops and with agricultural
491 losses identified as the “Key risk 2” by IPCC (Bednar-Friedl et al.; 2022), flash droughts
492 require our attention to mitigate such risks to agricultural crops and natural ecosystems.

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501 **Authors Contribution**

502 OR and RK conceived the idea and designed the experimental design. DY carried out
503 the analysis with the support of JS and VT. DY wrote the initial draft with inputs from
504 OR and RK, MH and everybody contributed in writing and editing the script.

505 **Data availability statements**

506 ISIMIP data used in the study can be obtained from ISIMIP repository
507 (<https://data.isimip.org/>). The study then uses warming levels provided by ISIMIP
508 protocol website ([https://www.isimip.org/protocol/isimip3b-temperature-thresholds-
509 and-time-slices/](https://www.isimip.org/protocol/isimip3b-temperature-thresholds-and-time-slices/)) to get the year of different warming levels under different scenarios
510 and GCMs.

511 **References**

512 Bednar-Friedl, B., Biesbroek, G., Schmidt, D. N., Alexander, P., Børshiem, K. Y.,
513 Carnicer, J., Georgopoulou, E., Haasnoot, M., Le Cozannet, G., Lionello, P. et al.

- (2022). Europe: from chapters and cross-chapter papers, *Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability*, Cambridge University Press, pp. 1817–1927.
- Bevacqua, E., Rakovec, O., Schumacher, D. L., Kumar, R., Thober, S., Samaniego, L., Seneviratne, S. I. and Zscheischler, J. (2024). Direct and lagged climate change effects intensified the 2022 european drought, *Nature Geoscience* pp. 1–8.
- Boyer, J., Byrne, P., Cassman, K., Cooper, M., Delmer, D., Greene, T., Gruis, F., Habben, J., Hausmann, N., Kenny, N. et al. (2013). The us drought of 2012 in perspective: a call to action, *Global Food Security* **2**(3): 139–143.
- Büntgen, U., Urban, O., Krusic, P. J., Rybníček, M., Kolář, T., Kyncl, T., Ač, A., Koňasová, E., Čáslavský, J., Esper, J. et al. (2021). Recent european drought extremes beyond common era background variability, *Nature Geoscience* **14**(4): 190–196.
- Chen, L. G., Gottschalck, J., Hartman, A., Miskus, D., Tinker, R. and Artusa, A. (2019). Flash drought characteristics based on US drought monitor, *Atmosphere* **10**(9): 498.
- Christian, J. I., Basara, J. B., Hunt, E. D., Otkin, J. A., Furtado, J. C., Mishra, V., Xiao, X. and Randall, R. M. (2021). Global distribution, trends, and drivers of flash drought occurrence, *Nature communications* **12**(1): 1–11.
- Christian, J. I., Basara, J. B., Hunt, E. D., Otkin, J. A. and Xiao, X. (2020). Flash drought development and cascading impacts associated with the 2010 Russian heatwave, *Environmental Research Letters* **15**(9): 094078.
- Christian, J. I., Basara, J. B., Otkin, J. A. and Hunt, E. D. (2019). Regional characteristics of flash droughts across the United States, *Environmental Research Communications* **1**(12): 125004.
- Christian, J. I., Hobbins, M., Hoell, A., Otkin, J. A., Ford, T. W., Cravens, A. E., Powlen, K. A., Wang, H. and Mishra, V. (2024). Flash drought: A state of the science review, *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Water* **11**(3): e1714.
- Christian, J. I., Martin, E. R., Basara, J. B., Furtado, J. C., Otkin, J. A., Lowman, L. E., Hunt, E. D., Mishra, V. and Xiao, X. (2023). Global projections of flash drought show increased risk in a warming climate, *Communications Earth & Environment* **4**(1): 165.
- Climate Action Tracker (2021). Climate action tracker, <https://climateactiontracker.org/methodology/paris-temperature-goal/>. Accessed: 2025-04-10.
- Droppers, B., Rakovec, O., Avila, L., Azimi, S., Cortés-Torres, N., De León Pérez, D., Imhoff, R., Francés, F., Kollet, S., Rigon, R. et al. (2024). Multi-model hydrological reference dataset over continental europe and an african basin, *Scientific Data* **11**(1): 1009.
- Fan, J., McConkey, B., Wang, H. and Janzen, H. (2016). Root distribution by depth for temperate agricultural crops, *Field Crops Research* **189**: 68–74.
- Ford, T. W. and Labosier, C. F. (2017). Meteorological conditions associated with the

- 553 onset of flash drought in the eastern United States, *Agricultural and forest meteorology*
554 **247**: 414–423.
- 555 Goswami, P. and Gallant, A. J. (2025). Understanding drought onset: What makes
556 flash droughts different from conventional droughts?, *Weather and Climate Extremes*
557 p. 100782.
- 558 Gringorten, I. I. (1963). A plotting rule for extreme probability paper, *Journal of*
559 *Geophysical Research* **68**(3): 813–814.
- 560 Gu, L., Schumacher, D. L., Fischer, E. M., Slater, L. J., Yin, J., Sippel, S., Chen, J.,
561 Liu, P. and Knutti, R. (2025). Flash drought impacts on global ecosystems amplified
562 by extreme heat, *Nature Geoscience* pp. 1–7.
- 563 Hari, V., Rakovec, O., Markonis, Y., Hanel, M. and Kumar, R. (2020). Increased future
564 occurrences of the exceptional 2018–2019 Central European drought under global
565 warming, *Scientific reports* **10**(1): 1–10.
- 566 Hurtt, G. C., Chini, L., Sahajpal, R., Frothing, S., Bodirsky, B. L., Calvin, K., Doelman,
567 J. C., Fisk, J., Fujimori, S., Goldewijk, K. K. et al. (2020). Harmonization of
568 global land-use change and management for the period 850–2100 (luh2) for cmip6,
569 *Geoscientific Model Development Discussions* **2020**: 1–65.
- 570 IPCC (2018). Global Warming of 1.5°C. An IPCC Special Report on the impacts of
571 global warming of 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels and related global greenhouse
572 gas emission pathways, <https://www.ipcc.ch/sr15/>. Intergovernmental Panel on
573 Climate Change.
- 574 ISIMIP (2021). Isimip3b temperature thresholds and time slices, [https://www.isimip.](https://www.isimip.org/protocol/isimip3b-temperature-thresholds-and-time-slices/)
575 [org/protocol/isimip3b-temperature-thresholds-and-time-slices/](https://www.isimip.org/protocol/isimip3b-temperature-thresholds-and-time-slices/). Accessed:
576 2025-04-10.
- 577 Jing, Y., Wang, S., Chan, P. W. and Yang, Z.-L. (2025). Gross primary productivity is
578 more sensitive to accelerated flash droughts, *Communications Earth & Environment*
579 **6**(1): 34.
- 580 Koster, R. D., Liu, Q., Reichle, R. H. and Huffman, G. J. (2021). Improved estimates
581 of pentad precipitation through the merging of independent precipitation data sets,
582 *Water Resources Research* **57**(12): e2021WR030330.
- 583 Koster, R., Schubert, S., Wang, H., Mahanama, S. and DeAngelis, A. M. (2019).
584 Flash drought as captured by reanalysis data: Disentangling the contributions of
585 precipitation deficit and excess evapotranspiration, *Journal of Hydrometeorology*
586 **20**(6): 1241–1258.
- 587 Kumar, R., Hesse, F., Rao, P. S. C., Musolff, A., Jawitz, J. W., Sarrazin, F., Samaniego,
588 L., Fleckenstein, J. H., Rakovec, O., Thober, S. et al. (2020). Strong hydroclimatic
589 controls on vulnerability to subsurface nitrate contamination across europe, *Nature*
590 *communications* **11**(1): 6302.
- 591 Kumar, R., Samaniego, L. and Attinger, S. (2013). Implications of distributed hydrologic

- 592 model parameterization on water fluxes at multiple scales and locations, *Water*
593 *Resources Research* **49**(1): 360–379.
- 594 Lange, S. and Büchner, M. (2021). Isimip3b bias-adjusted atmospheric climate input
595 data (v1. 1).
- 596 Mahto, S. S. and Mishra, V. (2020). Dominance of summer monsoon flash droughts in
597 India, *Environmental Research Letters* **15**(10): 104061.
- 598 Mahto, S. S. and Mishra, V. (2023). Increasing risk of simultaneous occurrence of flash
599 drought in major global croplands, *Environmental Research Letters* **18**(4): 044044.
- 600 Manning, C., Widmann, M., Bevacqua, E., Van Loon, A. F., Maraun, D. and Vrac,
601 M. (2018). Soil moisture drought in europe: a compound event of precipitation and
602 potential evapotranspiration on multiple time scales, *Journal of Hydrometeorology*
603 **19**(8): 1255–1271.
- 604 Masson-Delmotte, V. et al. (2018). Global warming of 1.5 c: An ipcc special report
605 on impacts of global warming of 1.5 c above pre-industrial levels and related global
606 greenhouse gas emission pathways, in the contex of strengthening the global response
607 to the theraat of blimate change, sustainable development, and efforts to eradicate
608 poverty, (*No Title*) .
- 609 Mishra, V., Aadhar, S. and Mahto, S. S. (2021). Anthropogenic warming and
610 intraseasonal summer monsoon variability amplify the risk of future flash droughts in
611 India, *Npj Climate and Atmospheric Science* **4**(1): 1–10.
- 612 Moreno, G., Obrador, J. J., Cubera, E. and Dupraz, C. (2005). Fine root distribution
613 in dehesas of central-western spain, *Plant and soil* **277**: 153–162.
- 614 Murray, V. and Ebi, K. L. (2012). Ipcc special report on managing the risks of extreme
615 events and disasters to advance climate change adaptation (srex).
- 616 Naumann, G., Cammalleri, C., Mentaschi, L. and Feyen, L. (2021). Increased economic
617 drought impacts in Europe with anthropogenic warming, *Nature Climate Change*
618 **11**(6): 485–491.
- 619 Noguera, I., Domínguez-Castro, F. and Vicente-Serrano, S. M. (2020). Characteristics
620 and trends of flash droughts in spain, 1961–2018, *Annals of the New York Academy*
621 *of Sciences* **1472**(1): 155–172.
- 622 O’Neill, B. C., Tebaldi, C., Van Vuuren, D. P., Eyring, V., Friedlingstein, P., Hurtt, G.,
623 Knutti, R., Kriegler, E., Lamarque, J.-F., Lowe, J. et al. (2016). The scenario model
624 intercomparison project (scenariomip) for cmip6, *Geoscientific Model Development*
625 **9**(9): 3461–3482.
- 626 Otkin, J. A., Svoboda, M., Hunt, E. D., Ford, T. W., Anderson, M. C., Hain, C. and
627 Basara, J. B. (2018). Flash droughts: A review and assessment of the challenges
628 imposed by rapid-onset droughts in the United States, *Bulletin of the American*
629 *Meteorological Society* **99**(5): 911–919.
- 630 O’Neill, B. C., Kriegler, E., Riahi, K., Ebi, K. L., Hallegatte, S., Carter, T. R., Mathur,
631 R. and Van Vuuren, D. P. (2014). A new scenario framework for climate change

- 632 research: the concept of shared socioeconomic pathways, *Climatic change* **122**: 387–
633 400.
- 634 Paris Agreement (2015). *Report of the conference of the parties to the United Nations*
635 *framework convention on climate change (21st session, 2015: Paris)*. Retrived
636 December, Vol. 4, HeinOnline, p. 2.
- 637 Pendergrass, A. G., Meehl, G. A., Pulwarty, R., Hobbins, M., Hoell, A., AghaKouchak,
638 A., Bonfils, C. J., Gallant, A. J., Hoerling, M., Hoffmann, D. et al. (2020). Flash
639 droughts present a new challenge for subseasonal-to-seasonal prediction, *Nature*
640 *Climate Change* **10**(3): 191–199.
- 641 Pierce, D. W., Cayan, D. R., Maurer, E. P., Abatzoglou, J. T. and Hegewisch, K. C.
642 (2015). Improved bias correction techniques for hydrological simulations of climate
643 change, *Journal of Hydrometeorology* **16**(6): 2421–2442.
- 644 Pohl, F., Rakovec, O., Rebmann, C., Hildebrandt, A., Boeing, F., Hermanns,
645 F., Attinger, S., Samaniego, L. and Kumar, R. (2023). Long-term daily
646 hydrometeorological drought indices, soil moisture, and evapotranspiration for icos
647 sites, *Scientific Data* **10**(1): 281.
- 648 Pulwarty, R. S. and Sivakumar, M. V. (2014). Information systems in a changing climate:
649 Early warnings and drought risk management, *Weather and Climate Extremes* **3**: 14–
650 21.
- 651 Qing, Y., Wang, S., Ancell, B. C. and Yang, Z.-L. (2022). Accelerating flash droughts
652 induced by the joint influence of soil moisture depletion and atmospheric aridity,
653 *Nature communications* **13**(1): 1139.
- 654 Rakovec, O., Kumar, R., Mai, J., Cuntz, M., Thober, S., Zink, M., Attinger, S., Schäfer,
655 D., Schrön, M. and Samaniego, L. (2016). Multiscale and multivariate evaluation
656 of water fluxes and states over european river basins, *Journal of Hydrometeorology*
657 **17**(1): 287–307.
- 658 Rakovec, O., Samaniego, L., Hari, V., Markonis, Y., Moravec, V., Thober, S., Hanel,
659 M. and Kumar, R. (2022). The 2018–2020 multi-year drought sets a new benchmark
660 in europe, *Earth's Future* **10**(3): e2021EF002394.
- 661 Řehoř, J., Brázdil, R., Trnka, M. and Balek, J. (2024). Flash droughts in central europe
662 and their circulation drivers, *Climate Dynamics* **62**(2): 1107–1121.
- 663 Rosa, L. and Sangiorgio, M. (2025). Global water gaps under future warming levels,
664 *Nature Communications* **16**(1): 1192.
- 665 Samaniego, L., Kumar, R. and Attinger, S. (2010). Multiscale parameter regionalization
666 of a grid-based hydrologic model at the mesoscale, *Water Resources Research* **46**(5).
- 667 Samaniego, L., Thober, S., Kumar, R., Wanders, N., Rakovec, O., Pan, M., Zink, M.,
668 Sheffield, J., Wood, E. F. and Marx, A. (2018). Anthropogenic warming exacerbates
669 european soil moisture droughts, *Nature Climate Change* **8**(5): 421–426.
- 670 Schenk, H. J. and Jackson, R. B. (2002). The global biogeography of roots, *Ecological*
671 *monographs* **72**(3): 311–328.

- 672 Shah, J., Hari, V., Rakovec, O., Markonis, Y., Samaniego, L., Mishra, V., Hanel, M.,
673 Hinz, C. and Kumar, R. (2022). Increasing footprint of climate warming on flash
674 droughts occurrence in europe, *Environmental Research Letters* **17**(6): 064017.
- 675 Shah, J., Kumar, R., Samaniego, L., Markonis, Y., Hanel, M., Attinger, S., Hari, V.
676 and Rakovec, O. (2023). On the role of antecedent meteorological conditions on flash
677 drought initialization in Europe, *Environmental Research Letters* **18**(6): 064039.
- 678 Silvestri, L., Saraceni, M., Brunone, B., Meniconi, S., Passadore, G. and
679 Bongioannini Cerlini, P. (2025). Assessment of seasonal soil moisture forecasts over
680 the central mediterranean, *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* **29**(4): 925–946.
- 681 Sreeparvathy, V. and Srinivas, V. V. (2022). Meteorological flash droughts risk
682 projections based on CMIP6 climate change scenarios, *npj Climate and Atmospheric*
683 *Science* **5**(1): 1–17. Number: 1 Publisher: Nature Publishing Group.
- 684 Sungmin, O. and Park, S. K. (2023). Flash drought drives rapid vegetation stress in
685 arid regions in europe, *Environmental Research Letters* **18**(1): 014028.
- 686 Sungmin, O. and Park, S. K. (2024). Global ecosystem responses to flash droughts are
687 modulated by background climate and vegetation conditions, *Communications Earth*
688 *& Environment* **5**(1): 88.
- 689 Svoboda, M., LeComte, D., Hayes, M., Heim, R., Gleason, K., Angel, J., Rippey, B.,
690 Tinker, R., Palecki, M., Stooksbury, D. et al. (2002). The drought monitor, *Bulletin*
691 *of the American Meteorological Society* **83**(8): 1181–1190.
- 692 Vautard, R., Gobiet, A., Sobolowski, S., Kjellström, E., Stegehuis, A., Watkiss, P.,
693 Mendlik, T., Landgren, O., Nikulin, G., Teichmann, C. et al. (2014). The european
694 climate under a 2 c global warming, *Environmental Research Letters* **9**(3): 034006.
- 695 Wang, M., Menzel, L., Jiang, S., Ren, L., Xu, C.-Y. and Cui, H. (2023). Evaluation of
696 flash drought under the impact of heat wave events in southwestern germany, *Science*
697 *of the Total Environment* **904**: 166815.
- 698 Wang, Y. and Yuan, X. (2022). The anthropogenic acceleration and intensification
699 of flash drought over the southeastern coastal region of china will continue into the
700 future, *Atmospheric and Oceanic Science Letters* **15**(5): 100262.
- 701 Warszawski, L., Frieler, K., Huber, V., Piontek, F., Serdeczny, O. and Schewe, J.
702 (2014). The inter-sectoral impact model intercomparison project (isi-mip): project
703 framework, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **111**(9): 3228–3232.
- 704 Xu, H., Zhu, Y., Yagci, A. L., Lü, H., Gou, Q., Wang, X., Liu, E., Ding, Z., Pan, Y.,
705 Liu, D. et al. (2023). Development of composite drought indices for the coastal areas
706 of southeastern china: A case study of jinjiang and jiulongjiang river basins, *Journal*
707 *of Hydrology* **626**: 130210.
- 708 Yuan, X., Ma, Z., Pan, M. and Shi, C. (2015). Microwave remote sensing of short-term
709 droughts during crop growing seasons, *Geophysical Research Letters* **42**(11): 4394–
710 4401.

- 711 Yuan, X., Wang, L., Wood, E. F. et al. (2018). Anthropogenic intensification of southern
712 african flash droughts as exemplified by the 2015/16 season, *Bulletin of the American*
713 *Meteorological Society* **99**(1): S86–S90.
- 714 Yuan, X., Wang, L., Wu, P., Ji, P., Sheffield, J. and Zhang, M. (2019). Anthropogenic
715 shift towards higher risk of flash drought over China, *Nature communications* **10**(1): 1–
716 8.
- 717 Yuan, X., Wang, Y., Ji, P., Wu, P., Sheffield, J. and Otkin, J. A. (2023). A global
718 transition to flash droughts under climate change, *Science* **380**(6641): 187–191.
- 719 Zeng, Z., Wu, W., Peñuelas, J., Li, Y., Jiao, W., Li, Z., Ren, X., Wang, K. and Ge, Q.
720 (2023). Increased risk of flash droughts with raised concurrent hot and dry extremes
721 under global warming, *npj Climate and Atmospheric Science* **6**(1): 134.

Figure 1: Spatial distribution of flash drought events at different warming levels. Panels (a)-(d) represent the number of flash drought events (FD Count (normalised according to the number of combinations available)) over each grid cell for the period of warming level ± 15 years for (a) the 1°C warming level (b) the 1.5°C warming level (c) the 2°C warming level, and (d) the 3°C warming level. Panels (e)-(g) illustrate the relative changes of flash drought events between different warming levels: (e) between 1.5°C and 1°C, (f) between 2°C and 1°C, (g) between 3°C and 1°C. Panel (h) presents a box plot of the ensemble mean of the flash drought event over a grid cell in the same 31-year (warming level year ± 15 years) period, normalised according to the number of combinations available across GCMs, under SSP126, SSP370 and SSP585 scenarios.

Figure 2: Flash drought area density distributions across Europe under different warming levels (see Supporting Information Table S1 for centre years of the 31-year period). Panel (a) shows the density distribution of the area across Europe under different warming levels, with the dashed vertical line showing the area under the ridge plot that is above 40% flash drought area across Europe. Panels (b)-(d) show the distribution across different regions of Europe, with (b) showcasing Northern Europe, (c) Central Europe, and (d) the Mediterranean. The number inside each density plot is the respective median value of the density plot. Panel (e) shows a box-plots of the area under flash drought across different European regions at different warming levels.

Figure 3: Bi-variate heatmaps of flash drought events categorized into various “bins” according to the prevailing meteorological conditions, i.e., temperature and precipitation anomalies going from 1°C warming level (left) to 1.5°C, 2°C and 3°C in the second column. The black outline shows the temperature precipitation anomaly region in which 90% of the flash drought grid/pixel count is concentrated. Each of the heatmaps is accompanied by the relative change along with the absolute differences (depicted by a circle enclosed into the bin) between a particular “bin” corresponding to 1°C warming level.

Figure 4: Sensitivity profile of the number of flash drought events and area with respect to each degree of warming. Panel (a) shows a linear fit curve of the flash drought frequency in the 31-year period of a warming level as we move from 1°C to 3°C warming level, along with the mean values at each degree of warming. Panel (b) shows the linear fit into the mean area under flash drought, along with the equations of each region and mean values. Bands in both the profiles represent standard error ($SE = SD/\sqrt{n}$)

Table S1: Years when different climate models reach specified global mean temperature (GMT) above the pre-industrial levels (in °C) under SSP1-2.6, SSP3-7.0, and SSP5-8.5 scenarios.

SSP126						
GMT (°C)	GFDL-ESM4	IPSL-CM6A-LR	MPI-ESM1-2-HR	MRI-ESM2-0	UKESM1-0-LL	
3.0	–	–	–	–	–	–
2.5	–	–	–	–	–	2059
2.0	–	2036	–	–	–	2036
1.5	–	2018	2047	2033	–	2023
1.0	2021	1999	2013	2015	–	2011
0.5	2000	1956	1988	1998	–	2000

SSP370						
GMT (°C)	GFDL-ESM4	IPSL-CM6A-LR	MPI-ESM1-2-HR	MRI-ESM2-0	UKESM1-0-LL	
3.0	2084	2055	2082	2075	–	2050
2.5	2070	2043	2067	2060	–	2040
2.0	2057	2032	2052	2047	–	2031
1.5	2042	2018	2036	2032	–	2022
1.0	2022	1999	2013	2015	–	2011
0.5	2000	1956	1988	1998	–	2000

SSP585						
GMT (°C)	GFDL-ESM4	IPSL-CM6A-LR	MPI-ESM1-2-HR	MRI-ESM2-0	UKESM1-0-LL	
3.0	2076	2050	2074	2065	–	2046
2.5	2065	2042	2063	2052	–	2039
2.0	2053	2031	2050	2039	–	2031
1.5	2039	2016	2034	2027	–	2022
1.0	2022	1999	2014	2014	–	2011
0.5	2000	1956	1988	1998	–	2000

Supplementary Figure S1: Pictorial representation of a flash drought event representing (a) start at the point where SMI falls from above 40th percentile to below 20th percentile in less than 3 pentads (b) decline rate at 0.1 SMI per pentad (c) termination at the sustenance level of above 20th percentile for at least 2 pentads (d) duration between 6-18 pentads

Supplementary Figure S2: Spatial distribution of flash drought events (FD Count) at different warming levels. Panels represent the number of flash drought events over each grid cell for the period of warming level ± 15 years for (a) the 0.5°C warming level (b) the 1.0°C warming level (c) the 1.5°C warming level (d) the 2.0°C warming level (e) the 2.5°C warming level, and (d) the 3.0°C warming level.

Supplementary Figure S3: Flash drought area density distributions and Sensitivity curves for croplands in Europe under different warming levels (see Supporting Information Table S1 for centre years of the 31-year period). Panel A(a) shows the density distribution of the area across European croplands under different warming levels, with the dashed vertical line showing the area under the ridge plot that is above 40% flash drought area across Europe. Panels A(b)-(d) show the distribution across croplands in different regions of Europe, with A(b) showcasing Northern Europe, A(c) Central Europe, and A(d) the Mediterranean. The number inside each density plot is the respective median value of the density plot. Panel B shows a box-plots of the cropland area under flash drought across different European regions at different warming levels. Panel C shows a linear fit of the flash drought events in the 31-year period of a warming level as we move from 1°C to 3°C warming level, along with the mean values at each degree of warming. Panel D shows the linear fit into the mean area under flash drought, along with the equations of each region and mean values. Bands in both the profiles represent standard error ($SE = SD/\sqrt{n}$)

Supplementary Figure S4: Flash drought area density distributions and Sensitivity curves for pasturelands in Europe under different warming levels (see Supporting Information Table S1 for centre years of the 31-year period). Panel A(a) shows the density distribution of the area across European pasturelands under different warming levels, with the dashed vertical line showing the area under the ridge plot that is above 40% flash drought area across Europe. Panels A(b)-(d) show the distribution across pasturelands in different regions of Europe, with A(b) showcasing Northern Europe, A(c) Central Europe, and A(d) the Mediterranean. The number inside each density plot is the respective median value of the density plot. Panel B shows a box-plots of the pastureland area under flash drought across different European regions at different warming levels. Panel C shows a linear fit of the flash drought events in the 31-year period of a warming level as we move from 1°C to 3°C warming level, along with the mean values at each degree of warming. Panel D shows the linear fit into the mean area under flash drought, along with the equations of each region and mean values. Bands in both the profiles represent standard error ($SE = SD/\sqrt{n}$)

Supplementary Figure S5: Flash drought area density distributions and Sensitivity curves for forests in Europe under different warming levels (see Supporting Information Table S1 for centre years of the 31-year period). Panel A(a) shows the density distribution of the area across European forests under different warming levels, with the dashed vertical line showing the area under the ridge plot that is above 40% flash drought area across Europe. Panels A(b)-(d) show the distribution across forests in different regions of Europe, with A(b) showcasing Northern Europe, A(c) Central Europe, and A(d) the Mediterranean. The number inside each density plot is the respective median value of the density plot. Panel B shows a box-plots of the forest area under flash drought across different European regions at different warming levels. Panel C shows a linear fit of the flash drought events in the 31-year period of a warming level as we move from 1°C to 3°C warming level, along with the mean values at each degree of warming. Panel D shows the linear fit into the mean area under flash drought, along with the equations of each region and mean values. Bands in both the profiles represent standard error ($SE = SD/\sqrt{n}$)

Supplementary Figure S6: Bi-variate heatmaps of flash drought events for the NEU region categorized into various “bins” according to the prevailing meteorological conditions, i.e., temperature and precipitation anomalies going from 1°C warming level (left) to 1.5°C, 2°C and 3°C in the second column. The black outline shows the temperature precipitation anomaly region in which 90% of the flash drought grid/pixel count is concentrated. Each of the heatmaps is accompanied with the relative change along with the absolute differences (depicted by a circle enclosed into the bin) between a particular “bin” corresponding to 1°C warming level.

Supplementary Figure S7: Bi-variate heatmaps of flash drought events for the CEU region categorized into various “bins” according to the prevailing meteorological conditions, i.e., temperature and precipitation anomalies going from 1°C warming level (left) to 1.5°C, 2°C and 3°C in the second column. The black outline shows the temperature precipitation anomaly region in which 90% of the flash drought grid/pixel count is concentrated. Each of the heatmaps is accompanied with the relative change along with the absolute differences (depicted by a circle enclosed into the bin) between a particular “bin” corresponding to 1°C warming level.

Supplementary Figure S8: Bi-variate heatmaps of flash drought events for the MED region categorized into various "bins" according to the prevailing meteorological conditions, i.e., temperature and precipitation anomalies going from 1°C warming level (left) to 1.5°C, 2°C and 3°C in the second column. The black outline shows the temperature precipitation anomaly region in which 90% of the flash drought grid/pixel count is concentrated. Each of the heatmaps is accompanied with the relative change along with the absolute differences (depicted by a circle enclosed into the bin) between a particular "bin" corresponding to 1°C warming level.

Supplementary Figure S9: Variation of area under flash drought in case of croplands for Entire Europe, NEU, CEU, MED under the three scenarios using an ensemble mean and showing a 30-year backwards moving average from 1981-2100. Used to study parallels between our study and Christian et al. (2023). Results are similar for the SSP585 and SSP126, which are the two common scenarios in the study.